

Online Appendix

The Low-Code Phenomenon: Mapping the Intellectual Structure of Research

Syed Asad Ali Naqvi¹, Markus P. Zimmer², Kristina Lemmer³, Paul Drews⁴, Rahul C. Basole⁵

Our literature review analysis included 105 publications from 2014-2022. Given page length constraints, a comprehensive reference list of is provided in this online appendix (available at <https://zenodo.org/record/8354060>).

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¹asadali.naqvi@outlook.com

²markus.zimmer@leuphana.de

³kristina.lemmer@leuphana.de

⁴paul.drews@leuphana.de

⁵rahul.basole@accenture.com

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